

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

PREDICTION PERFORMANCE OF RELATIONSHIPS AMONG MACROECONOMIC VARIABLES USING DEEP LEARNING AND DIFFERENTIAL EQUATIONS: THE CASE OF TURKEY

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the dynamic interactions and forecasting performance of key economic variables in Turkey from 2014 to 2024 using both linear ordinary differential equation (ODE) model and artificial neural networks (ANN). The ODE model captures instantaneous changes over time, while the ANN model accounts for nonlinear relationships among variables such as the US Dollar exchange rate, inflation, interest rates, economic growth, and geopolitical risks. Parameter estimation for the ODE system was performed using Runge-Kutta numerical solutions combined with least squares fitting, and the ANN model employed optimized activation functions for improved prediction accuracy. Comparative analysis shows that both models effectively predict trends, but the ANN model achieves better accuracy across all evaluation metrics. Impact analysis based on the ANN model reveals that economic growth and financial market indicators have strong positive effects on the exchange rate, while political uncertainties and external shocks tend to negatively impact it. These results highlight the sensitivity of the Turkish economy to both domestic and global factors, emphasizing the importance of stable economic policies to manage exchange rate volatility. The findings demonstrate that combining traditional mathematical modeling with machine learning techniques offers valuable insights and enhanced forecasting ability for emerging markets like Turkey, which face rapid structural changes and external risks.

Keywords: Economic Indicators, Artificial Neural Networks, Activation Function, Linear Differential Equation System.

1. INTRODUCTION

The relationships among macroeconomic variables exhibit a complex and dynamic structure. Analyzing these relationships is of great importance for achieving economic growth and developing appropriate economic policies (Çelik & Yılmaz, 2023). Inflation is the continuous increase in the prices of products within a specific basket of goods over time. This process weakens consumers' real purchasing power and causes the local currency to depreciate against foreign currencies (BritannicaEditors, 2025). High inflation reduces confidence in the economy, negatively affecting expectations and consumer confidence indices, while increasing investors' demand for foreign exchange as a hedge against the depreciation of the local currency (Sulestiyoko & Karamina, 2023).

A decrease in inflation linked to economic growth and an increase in employment positively affect expectations, enhance economic confidence, reduce the unemployment rate, and decrease foreign exchange demand due to the stabilization of the local currency's value (Aytekin & Bozkaya, 2021). Exchange rate fluctuations arising from changes in foreign exchange demand naturally affect the country's foreign trade (Kandil & Mirzaie, 2005).

As seen, the relationship among macroeconomic variables is complex. However, it is crucial for policy-

makers to thoroughly analyze and understand these interrelationships in order to implement effective economic policies (Wieland et al. 2023).

The purpose of this study is to analyze the relationships among selected macroeconomic indicators for Turkey using mathematical methods. The analysis evaluates monthly data between January 2014 and June 2024 for variables including the US dollar exchange rate, general economic expectation index, employment rate, unemployment rate, consumer price index, and consumer confidence index. Models are developed using both Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) and linear differential equation systems.

The second chapter presents a literature review related to the topic; the third chapter details the dataset and methodology; the fourth chapter discusses the findings; the fifth chapter presents the model prediction results; the sixth chapter analyzes the interactions among variables; and finally, the seventh chapter offers general conclusions and discussions.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

In the literature, deep learning and differential equations are frequently used especially in modeling dynamic control systems, solving optimization problems, image processing, physical system modeling, financial modeling, detecting relationships among variables and forecasting, as well as time series analysis. Most studies focus on comparing the performance of

various deep learning methods with traditional approaches.

Plakandaras et al. (2015) forecasted the monthly and daily spot prices of five selected exchange rates using different deep learning methods. In their study, Ensemble Empirical Mode Decomposition (EEMD), Multivariate Adaptive Regression Splines (MARS), and Support Vector Regression (SVR) were used to successfully predict exchange rates. In-sample and out-of-sample forecasting capabilities were superior compared to alternative models.

Aydın and Çavdar (2015) compared Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) with the traditional VAR time series method for exchange rate forecasting in Turkey and found ANN to perform better.

Bao et al. (2017) achieved high accuracy in financial time series forecasting by combining wavelet transform (WT), stacked autoencoders (SAE), and Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) deep learning models.

Ramakrishnan et al. (2017) compared Support Vector Machines, Neural Networks, and Random Forest methods for exchange rate forecasting in Malaysia, concluding that Random Forest produced the best results.

Jung et al. (2018) demonstrated that advanced methods such as Elastic Net, Super Learner, and Recurrent Neural Networks (RNN) outperform traditional models in macroeconomic forecasting.

Shapi et al. (2021) predicted energy consumption in buildings in Malaysia using Support Vector Machines, Artificial Neural Networks, and K-Nearest Neighbor algorithms, comparing performances via RMSE, NRMSE, and MAPE metrics.

Sohrabi et al. (2023) argued that traditional regression and time series methods are insufficient for national income forecasting, showing that Radial Basis

Function (RBF) neural networks provide better predictions.

Sabri et al. (2023) highlighted the superior performance of neural networks in forecasting Pakistan's macroeconomic indicators.

Gür (2024) stated that the Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) model outperforms other machine learning techniques in forecasting the BIST 100 index.

Şimşek (2024) compared various deep learning methods for exchange rate forecasting in Turkey and found Random Forest to yield the best performance.

Anesti et al. (2024) showed that machine learning models using text-based macroeconomic data perform better during crisis periods.

Daşbaşı and Taşyürek (2021) emphasized the superiority of differential equation models over traditional models in forecasting Turkey's economic growth.

Khoo et al. (2021) integrated neural networks with differential equation systems to successfully simulate the time-dependent changes of macroeconomic indicators.

Bobalova and Novotna (2022) investigated interactions among economic variables during crises using time-delayed linear differential equations and demonstrated that these systems are sensitive to sudden changes.

3. DATASET AND METHOD

Within the scope of this study, the variables presented in Table 1, which were obtained from the Turkish Statistical Institute (TSI) on a monthly basis between 2014:01 and 2024:06, were analyzed. Here, t denotes the time variable in days.

Table 1

State Variables		
Variable	Indicator	Definition
$x(t)$	USD Exchange Rate	Represents the value of the US Dollar against the Turkish Lira, a key measure for investment instruments ¹ .
$y(t)$	General Economic Outlook (Seasonally Adjusted)	Reflects consumer expectations regarding the overall state of the economy, adjusted for seasonal effects.
$z(t)$	Employment Rate (%)	Indicates the proportion of the working-age population that is currently employed.
$h(t)$	Unemployment Rate (%)	Shows the percentage of the labor force that is unemployed and actively seeking work.
$f(t)$	Consumer Price Index (2003=100)	Measures changes in the price level of a basket of goods and services consumed by households, using 2003 as the base year.
$g(t)$	Consumer Confidence Index (Seasonally Adjusted)	Gauges consumer sentiment on personal finances and the general economy, seasonally adjusted for consistency.

Therefore, the data obtained from TSI for the variables defined in Table 1 are presented in Table 2.

¹ According to TCMB data, the foreign currency ratio in total deposits in Turkey is approximately 57%. This ratio confirms that foreign currency is an important financial investment instrument in Turkey.

Table 2

Data (Turkish Statistical Institute)

Date	t (Day)	$x(t)$	$y(t)$	$z(t)$	$h(t)$	$f(t)$	$g(t)$
01.01.2014	0	7.77	94.0	43.2	10.3	254.32	91.8
01.02.2014	30	-0.60	90.4	44.1	10.2	254.64	89.5
01.03.2014	60	0.24	95.9	45.1	9.7	259.98	92.6
...
01.04.2024	3690	0.96	78.1	49.6	8.4	3237.61	80.5
01.05.2024	3720	-0.33	78.3	49.6	8.4	3292.35	80.5
01.06.2024	3750	1.00	76.1	49.6	8.4	3350.79	78.3

First of all, the data defined in Table 1 were normalized with min-max normalization. One of the most commonly used methods for normalizing data is “min-max normalization.” For each attribute, the lowest value is set to 0 and the highest value is set to 1. All other values are then adjusted to fall between 0 and 1 as decimals. Thus, for a variable x , the data set is created with the formula

$$x_{norm} = \frac{x - x_{min}}{x_{max} - x_{min}} \tag{1}$$

Some results obtained for the normalization process from the data set in Table 2 are given in Table 3.

Table 3

Some values for normalizing the dataset in Table 2.

	t	$x(t)$	$y(t)$	$z(t)$	$h(t)$	$f(t)$	$g(t)$
Minimum Value	0	-8.21	61.6	41.1	8.4	254.32	63.4
Maximum Value	3750	26.83	107	49.6	14.7	3350.79	97.4

The data set in Table 2 is normalized with min-max normalization and presented in Table 4.

Table 4

Normalized dataset

t_{norm}	x_{norm}	y_{norm}	z_{norm}	h_{norm}	f_{norm}	g_{norm}
0	0.45605	0.713656	0.247059	0.301587	0	0.835294
0.008	0.21718	0.634361	0.352941	0.285714	0.000103	0.767647
0.016	0.241153	0.755507	0.470588	0.206349	0.001828	0.858824
...
0.984	0.261701	0.363436	1	0	0.963449	0.502941
0.992	0.224886	0.367841	1	0	0.981127	0.502941
1	0.262842	0.319383	1	0	1	0.438235

For this analysis, mathematically presented and analyzed ANN activation functions and differential equation system were used. Data consisting of 126x6 dimensions were compiled from TSI. At the end of the study, the performances of the Linear Ordinary Differential Equation (ODE) system and ANN activation functions in estimating the real values of the variables were compared. The training, validation and testing processes of the ANN model were carried out with normalized data and the parameters of the Tangent Hyperbolic (tanh) activation function were determined as explained in detail in this section. ANN analysis was performed twice for each variable as the best and worst. After this process, two different optimization models were proposed as the ANN model and the linear ODE system using the normalized original data. Thus, each variable was estimated separately. Separate MSE val-

ues were calculated for each model with the data obtained as a result of the estimation. Thus, the process of revealing the model that predicts the variables given in Table 1 with the lowest error was carried out through comparative analysis.

3.1. Artificial Neural Network (ANN)

The structure of Artificial Neural Network (ANN) is based on the functioning of a single neuron as shown in Fig. 1. In this model, each input value ($x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots, x_n$) is multiplied by its corresponding weight ($w_1, w_2, w_3, \dots, w_n$) and then fed to the neuron. The weighted sum of all inputs is calculated at the input of the neuron and a result (s) is obtained, which is mathematically expressed as $s = \sum_{i=1}^n x_i w_i$ (Haykin, 1999). This represents the summation function as shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. ANN structure

The result is then passed through an activation function, which is usually a nonlinear mathematical function that determines the output of the neuron. The output is given by the formula $y = f(s)$, where f represents the activation function and y represents the predicted or calculated value. The role of the activation function is to introduce nonlinearity into the model, allowing the neural network to learn complex patterns and relationships in the data (Goodfellow, Bengio, & Courville, 2016). The output of this process is passed to the next layer and serves as the final output of the system. This structure forms the basic building block of an ANN, allowing it to process data through layers of interconnected neurons. The model is trained using backpropagation to minimize errors by adjusting the weights, which improves the network's prediction accuracy over time.

3.2. Ordinary Differential Equations (ODEs)

In the context of economic and dynamic systems modeling, Ordinary Differential Equations (ODEs) play an important role in capturing continuous changes in variables over time. ODEs are mathematical models that describe the relationship between a function and its derivatives and reflect how a system evolves with respect to the rate of change of its dependent variables. In many areas of science, ODEs are often used to model systems where variables evolve continuously over time (Radzicki & Sterman, 1994).

An ODE typically takes the form $\frac{dy}{dt} = f(t, y)$, where $y(t)$ is the dependent variable, t is the independent variable (usually time), and $f(t, y)$ is a function that describes the rate of change of y with respect to time. The solution of an ODE provides a time trajectory of the system, providing insight into how the variables interact and change dynamically. ODE models can be solved analytically or numerically, depending on the complexity of the equation and the nature of the system. Analytical solutions may be available for linear and relatively simple systems. However, for more complex and nonlinear systems, numerical methods such as the

Euler method, Runge-Kutta methods, or finite difference methods are often used to approximate solutions (Kreyszig, 2011).

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this section, two different optimization methods are presented. One is the ANN activation function, which is among the deep learning methods, and the other is the linear differential equation system. The variables used in the study were previously presented in Table 1. The ANN activation function estimates the corresponding output value based on the current values of the input variables. However, the model presented through the linear differential equation system represents an initial value problem, which provides time-dependent forward projections for all relevant variables. Here, while these two different optimization methods are analyzed based on the normalized values presented in Table 4, their performance comparison is conducted using the actual data given in Table 3.

4.1. ANN Analysis of Variables

ANN activation functions can take various forms such as ReLU, PReLU, Tansig, Logsig, or Purelin (Goodfellow et al., 2016). In this study, based on previous experiments, the best-performing activation function was identified as a nonlinear structure incorporating both the Tansig and Logsig functions within two hidden layers. This activation function is presented in Equation (2).

$$u = (b_3)_{1 \times 1} + (LW_2)_{1 \times 6} \text{logsig}((b_2)_{6 \times 1} + (LW)_{6 \times 6} \text{tansig}((b_1)_{6 \times 1} + (IW)_{6 \times 5} v)) \quad (02)$$

where u represents the output variable, and $v = (v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n)^T$ represents the input variables. Additionally, each variable presented in Table 1 was analyzed six times, with one variable serving as the output and the remaining five as inputs. Moreover, since the ANN function can produce different results each time it is run, two trials were conducted for each analysis — one yielding the best and the other the worst result.

Therefore, the corresponding coefficients for the activation function were generated a total of 12 times. However, in the results section, only the coefficients from the best-performing activation function were

compared with the predictions of the differential equation system model. The related ANN architecture is shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Used ANN architecture

In the analysis, 70% of the data presented in Table 4 was used for training, 15% for validation, and 15% for testing. Additionally, the some metrical results obtained for each variable are given in Table 5.

Table 5

Results of ANN Training Process and Outcomes			
Output	Analysis	MSE	R
x_{norm}	Analysis 1	0.0010541	0.97195
	Analysis 2 (Best)	0.00049308	0.98698
y_{norm}	Analysis 1	0.00013549	0.99869
	Analysis 2 (Best)	9.7619e-05	0.99905
z_{norm}	Analysis 1	0.00070301	0.99222
	Analysis 2 (Best)	0.00052399	0.99421
h_{norm}	Analysis 1 (Best)	0.00035381	0.99713
	Analysis 2	0.00072826	0.99409
f_{norm}	Analysis 1 (Best)	1.0021e-05	0.99992
	Analysis 2	0.00042185	0.97148
g_{norm}	Analysis 1 (Best)	3.131e-05	0.99968
	Analysis 2	3.7336e-05	0.93952

The coefficients of the activation function in the equation given in (2) for each variable are given in Table 6. Here, the best performing ANN activation function is taken into account.

Table 6

Coefficients of ANN Activation Function with Minimum MSE		
	For x_{norm}	For y_{norm}
b_1 b_2 b_3	$\begin{pmatrix} -3.7778 \\ -3.2226 \\ 9.8087 \\ -17.8727 \\ -2.5020 \\ -2.5104 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} 1687.8 \\ 122.5 \\ 850.5 \\ -1211 \\ -6681.6 \\ -1080.8 \end{pmatrix}, (27.1389)$	$\begin{pmatrix} 8.8162 \\ 8.6504 \\ 10.8269 \\ -4.8519 \\ -3.2844 \\ -0.0339 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} 1.8 \\ -0.6 \\ 3.9 \\ -5.5 \\ 4.1 \\ 6569 \end{pmatrix}, (-13.2877)$
IW	$\begin{pmatrix} -6.6671 \\ 2.3378 \\ -9.3251 \\ 28.1491 \\ 20.3317 \\ -5.8175 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} 17.3795 \\ -4.8716 \\ 1.1340 \\ 4.9255 \\ -0.7443 \\ -1.1110 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} -47.4584 \\ -4.1863 \\ 1.4067 \\ 1.4086 \\ -0.3147 \\ 3.2562 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} 3.4995 \\ 6.4237 \\ -6.8955 \\ -22.3780 \\ -1.9052 \\ 0.3821 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} 0.3095 \\ 0.7040 \\ -10.9789 \\ -1.7618 \\ 0.4566 \\ 11.0213 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} -6.2966 \\ -6.2894 \\ -43.4321 \\ 6.0630 \\ 4.4168 \\ 2.8471 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} -2.0305 \\ -2.0520 \\ 1.9515 \\ 2.4067 \\ 0.8154 \\ -2.2886 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} 3.8453 \\ 2.6577 \\ 29.2515 \\ -5.6824 \\ -2.7849 \\ 4.8209 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} -5.4479 \\ -5.4115 \\ 26.4183 \\ 3.1410 \\ 2.4764 \\ -3.7542 \end{pmatrix}$
LW	$1.0e + 03$ $\begin{pmatrix} -0.0010 \\ 0.0105 \\ 0.0023 \\ -0.0012 \\ -0.0007 \\ 0.0016 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} 0.0093 \\ 0.0018 \\ -0.0016 \\ -0.0019 \\ 0.0028 \\ -0.0063 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} 0.1378 \\ 0.0005 \\ -0.0019 \\ 0.6451 \\ -0.0001 \\ -0.0732 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} -2.4459 \\ -0.0017 \\ -0.0003 \\ -0.0001 \\ 0.0011 \\ 1.6421 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} -4.2685 \\ -0.1288 \\ -0.8528 \\ 0.5659 \\ 6.6807 \\ 2.7942 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} 0.0147 \\ -0.0149 \\ -0.0016 \\ -0.0002 \\ 0.0024 \\ -0.0121 \end{pmatrix}$	$1.0e + 03$ * $\begin{pmatrix} -0.0028 \\ -0.0462 \\ -0.0812 \\ 0.0016 \\ 0.0047 \\ 0.0213 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} 0.0005 \\ -0.0559 \\ 0.0790 \\ 0.0034 \\ -0.0027 \\ -0.0210 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} 0.0004 \\ -0.0001 \\ -0.0056 \\ -0.0003 \\ 0.0004 \\ 6.5660 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} -0.0010 \\ -0.0105 \\ -0.0200 \\ -0.0006 \\ -0.0035 \\ 0.0027 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} -0.0025 \\ 0.0038 \\ 0.0206 \\ -0.0028 \\ 0.0006 \\ 0.0028 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} -0.0002 \\ 0.0007 \\ -0.0105 \\ -0.0001 \\ 0.0002 \\ -0.0005 \end{pmatrix}$
LW_2	$(-31.4558 \ 4.4281 \ 4.5801 \ 5.8684 \ 6.4079 \ -32.6750)$	$(14.8633 \ -0.6309 \ -0.2074 \ -14.5548 \ 12.7115 \ 0.8692)$

	For Z_{norm}	For I_{norm}
b_1 b_2 b_3	$\begin{pmatrix} 30.2234 \\ 10.0047 \\ 23.1772 \\ -4.2662 \\ 1.6755 \\ -2.7190 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 1453.1 \\ -88.7 \\ -138.8 \\ -457.4 \\ 90.6 \\ 398.1 \end{pmatrix}, (-467.5027)$	$\begin{pmatrix} 1.0821 \\ -2.9857 \\ 0.1849 \\ 5.5950 \\ 2.5301 \\ 4.2565 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} -21.6579 \\ -5.9332 \\ -7.4574 \\ 7.4687 \\ -2.4680 \\ -331.0754 \end{pmatrix}, (-1.5582)$
IW	$\begin{pmatrix} -1.2411 & -2.9229 & -14.5544 & -11.2224 & -24.6237 \\ -2.44490 & -7.2297 & -13.3207 & -8.66350 & 5.25670 \\ -14.9932 & -44.7491 & -0.8235 & 26.0288 & 6.0695 \\ 1.4780 & 10.5074 & 8.8435 & -0.6371 & -12.6905 \\ -0.0288 & 0.0299 & -0.1652 & 4.1149 & -0.0639 \\ 4.5421 & -15.0449 & -29.1433 & 80.5179 & 43.6904 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} -0.6321 & -0.5868 & -6.5906 & 22.6877 & -2.1483 \\ 1.0462 & 1.4819 & 1.2691 & 0.1198 & 1.9246 \\ -0.8346 & -1.0117 & -0.9168 & -1.3985 & 1.4497 \\ 4.5835 & 10.6667 & -11.3493 & 1.9076 & -4.5814 \\ 0.2278 & 1.4408 & 1.7203 & -13.9002 & -6.6428 \\ 2.6808 & 6.4145 & -4.2224 & 1.0484 & -7.5164 \end{pmatrix}$
LW	$1.0e + 03 * \begin{pmatrix} -0.0022 & 0.0013 & 0.0004 & -0.0034 & 0.0938 & -1.5352 \\ 0.0082 & -0.0061 & -0.2353 & -0.0130 & 0.0856 & -0.2397 \\ 0.0377 & 0.0475 & -0.1270 & 0.1788 & 0.2020 & -0.0822 \\ -0.7601 & 0.0534 & 0.0011 & 2.0316 & 1.0477 & 2.1902 \\ 0.4131 & 0.0039 & -0.4132 & -0.0001 & -0.0928 & 0.0002 \\ 0.3745 & 0.0041 & -0.6855 & -0.0001 & -0.0892 & 0.0001 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} 2.4942 & -12.1194 & -40.4149 & 5.9914 & 2.7997 & -23.5256 \\ -0.6115 & -1.5400 & -9.3291 & 0.3415 & -0.0604 & -3.1558 \\ -1.4585 & 6.2878 & 4.7695 & 11.9260 & 10.6864 & -6.3224 \\ 1.0570 & 5.6656 & 11.6311 & -3.2923 & 8.6578 & 7.6344 \\ -0.7418 & -2.1153 & -4.0630 & 0.2374 & -2.9441 & -0.9319 \\ -324.9961 & 6.1043 & 4.6922 & 12.1084 & 10.5931 & -6.4296 \end{pmatrix}$
LW_2	$(468.4419 \quad 0.6452 \quad -0.5795 \quad -0.2460 \quad -20.3885 \quad 20.3059)$	$(0.3918 \quad -1.3490 \quad -114.8295 \quad 1.3104 \quad 2.3129 \quad 114.0177)$

	For f_{norm}	For g_{norm}
b_1 b_2 b_3	$\begin{pmatrix} 2.5763 \\ -6.5179 \\ 1.0310 \\ 1.3885 \\ -0.6211 \\ 4.4814 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} 7.5884 \\ -1.5124 \\ -10.0272 \\ 11.1240 \\ 28.7741 \\ 29.0681 \end{pmatrix}, (39.2718)$	$\begin{pmatrix} -0.2280 \\ -4.1870 \\ -5.5849 \\ 0.9904 \\ 1.6654 \\ -3.7427 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} 65.2351 \\ -58.4441 \\ 30.5183 \\ -238.2181 \\ 1.6123 \\ -43.6693 \end{pmatrix}, (-1.4182)$
IW	$\begin{pmatrix} -0.9995 & 1.8355 & -3.8188 & -0.3466 & -0.6500 \\ 1.3933 & -3.6873 & 3.8826 & 0.5355 & 4.1467 \\ 1.4318 & 3.6204 & -0.0761 & -0.5480 & -6.0613 \\ 1.5635 & 2.0283 & -1.0563 & 0.9185 & -5.8583 \\ 2.2720 & -6.6232 & 2.8357 & -2.3948 & 6.2309 \\ -7.9655 & -0.4177 & -0.1054 & -5.3832 & -3.7124 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} 0.4057 & -0.2576 & -0.4211 & -0.3858 & -1.5537 \\ -1.3354 & 5.7616 & 1.8915 & 4.3532 & 1.0705 \\ -6.3802 & 0.1167 & 11.4408 & 6.1260 & 0.0499 \\ 0.0248 & -0.2451 & 0.0145 & 0.0394 & -0.1860 \\ 0.2986 & -6.5873 & 1.8439 & 4.9145 & -15.4348 \\ -5.2921 & -4.9632 & 5.0087 & 6.6870 & -0.5146 \end{pmatrix}$
LW	$\begin{pmatrix} -6.7911 & -2.2995 & -8.1032 & 12.4805 & -6.2883 & -2.5877 \\ 0.0232 & 1.2883 & 0.0144 & -0.0071 & -0.0008 & 0.0495 \\ -0.0141 & -16.6659 & 15.8743 & -13.5536 & 0.2141 & 4.9661 \\ 0.0603 & 17.8115 & -15.9688 & 13.6263 & -0.1969 & -4.9511 \\ 5.0435 & 28.9403 & -11.5348 & 10.7383 & 3.8881 & -1.6107 \\ 5.0393 & 29.1140 & -11.7425 & 10.8911 & 3.8127 & -1.6625 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} 27.4351 & 0.6031 & 5.1036 & -75.6101 & 0.5766 & 2.3538 \\ -2.0829 & 2.0750 & 1.3687 & 79.4575 & -1.5286 & -2.7290 \\ 22.0969 & -1.5399 & 5.1686 & -1.4930 & 4.6744 & 19.6853 \\ -20.7920 & 1.6779 & 13.3285 & 304.9217 & -9.6138 & -7.4869 \\ 1.3846 & 0.0016 & 0.2445 & -6.9978 & 0.1079 & 0.1127 \\ 12.9203 & 2.5664 & 7.0009 & 66.9249 & -0.3234 & -5.3451 \end{pmatrix}$
LW_2	$(-0.1745 \quad 69.7279 \quad -42.6200 \quad -42.2862 \quad -38.1308 \quad 37.5586)$	$(-0.4181 \quad 0.9952 \quad -0.1804 \quad -0.1620 \quad 104.1712 \quad -0.3221)$

4.2. Analysis of Linear Differential Equation Model of Variables

The proposed linear differential equation model for $t_{norm} \geq t_{norm_0}$ to represent the time parameter t and the independent variable is as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{dx_{norm}}{dt_{norm}} &= \delta_1 + \delta_2 x_{norm} + \delta_3 y_{norm} + \delta_4 z_{norm} + \delta_5 h_{norm} + \delta_6 f_{norm} + \delta_7 g_{norm} \\
 \frac{dy_{norm}}{dt_{norm}} &= \delta_8 + \delta_9 x_{norm} + \delta_{10} y_{norm} + \delta_{11} z_{norm} + \delta_{12} h_{norm} + \delta_{13} f_{norm} + \delta_{14} g_{norm} \\
 \frac{dz_{norm}}{dt_{norm}} &= \delta_{15} + \delta_{16} x_{norm} + \delta_{17} y_{norm} + \delta_{18} z_{norm} + \delta_{19} h_{norm} + \delta_{20} f_{norm} + \delta_{21} g_{norm} \\
 \frac{dh_{norm}}{dt_{norm}} &= \delta_{22} + \delta_{23} x_{norm} + \delta_{24} y_{norm} + \delta_{25} z_{norm} + \delta_{26} h_{norm} + \delta_{27} f_{norm} + \delta_{28} g_{norm} \\
 \frac{df_{norm}}{dt_{norm}} &= \delta_{29} + \delta_{30} x_{norm} + \delta_{31} y_{norm} + \delta_{32} z_{norm} + \delta_{33} h_{norm} + \delta_{34} f_{norm} + \delta_{35} g_{norm} \\
 \frac{dg_{norm}}{dt_{norm}} &= \delta_{36} + \delta_{37} x_{norm} + \delta_{38} y_{norm} + \delta_{39} z_{norm} + \delta_{40} h_{norm} + \delta_{41} f_{norm} + \delta_{42} g_{norm} \\
 x_{norm}(t_{norm_0}) &= x_{norm_0}, y_{norm}(t_{norm_0}) = y_{norm_0}, z_{norm}(t_{norm_0}) = z_{norm_0}, \\
 h_{norm}(t_{norm_0}) &= h_{norm_0}, f_{norm}(t_{norm_0}) = f_{norm_0}, g_{norm}(t_{norm_0}) = g_{norm_0}
 \end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

where $x_{norm} \equiv x_{norm}(t_{norm})$, $y_{norm} \equiv y_{norm}(t_{norm})$, $z_{norm} \equiv z_{norm}(t_{norm})$, $h_{norm} \equiv h_{norm}(t_{norm})$, $f_{norm} \equiv f_{norm}(t_{norm})$ and $g_{norm} \equiv g_{norm}(t_{norm})$. The ODE model in the equation system (3) was solved with the Matlab R2023a program `rungekutta 45` and then the parameter values closest to the values in Table 4 (giving the minimum error) were found using the `lsqcurvefit` function. In this context, the approach in (Işık & Daşbaşı, 2023) was used. Therefore, the δ_i parameters for $i = 1, 2, \dots, 42$ are presented in Table 7.

Table 7

$\delta_1 = -10.9880$	$\delta_8 = 48.31612$	$\delta_{15} = -15.38744$	$\delta_{22} = -1.72322$	$\delta_{29} = 2.11612$	$\delta_{36} = 39.35669$
$\delta_2 = 4.09144$	$\delta_9 = -56.46067$	$\delta_{16} = 31.02907$	$\delta_{23} = 0.52419$	$\delta_{30} = -1.67275$	$\delta_{37} = -47.31489$
$\delta_3 = 10.04783$	$\delta_{10} = 4.75934$	$\delta_{17} = 24.50088$	$\delta_{24} = -38.49686$	$\delta_{31} = 5.08749$	$\delta_{38} = 1.55286$
$\delta_4 = 3.34970$	$\delta_{11} = -25.25372$	$\delta_{18} = 2.21396$	$\delta_{25} = 3.20221$	$\delta_{32} = 0.69285$	$\delta_{39} = -19.88541$
$\delta_5 = 8.25045$	$\delta_{12} = -20.91157$	$\delta_{19} = 3.58898$	$\delta_{26} = -2.51115$	$\delta_{33} = -0.98887$	$\delta_{40} = -18.46080$
$\delta_6 = 5.51028$	$\delta_{13} = -2.43623$	$\delta_{20} = 3.80814$	$\delta_{27} = -3.60432$	$\delta_{34} = 3.74954$	$\delta_{41} = -0.85557$
$\delta_7 = -3.20503$	$\delta_{14} = -14.78928$	$\delta_{21} = -15.42634$	$\delta_{28} = 33.91177$	$\delta_{35} = -6.30448$	$\delta_{42} = -9.46407$

The denormalized numerical solutions of the equation system (3), obtained using the parameter values listed in Table 7, are compared with the actual data presented in Table 2. The corresponding graphical comparisons are illustrated in Figures 3 through 8.

Fig. 3. Graphical representation of the proposed equation system (3) for $x(t)$

Fig. 4. Graphical representation of the proposed equation system (3) for $y(t)$

Fig. 5. Graphical representation of the proposed equation system (3) for $z(t)$

Fig. 6. Graphical representation of the proposed equation system (3) for $h(t)$

Fig. 7. Graphical representation of the proposed equation system (3) for $f(t)$

Fig. 8. Graphical representation of the proposed equation system (3) for $g(t)$

5. ESTIMATION RESULTS

Here, the performances of the ANN and ODE models used according to the actual values given in Table 2 between 1.01.2014-1.06.2024 for the variables mentioned in Table 1 were compared according to various metrics. It was stated that the ANN estimate was made twice. Therefore, the ANN estimate with the best performance was taken into account. The estimated values of the methods used are shown in Table 8.

Table 8

Estimation Values of ANN and ODE Models

$x(t)$			$y(t)$			$z(t)$			$h(t)$			$f(t)$			$g(t)$		
Real	ANN Estimate	ODE Estimate	Real	ANN Estimate	ODE Estimate	Real	ANN Estimate	ODE Estimate	Real	ANN Estimate	ODE Estimate	Real	ANN Estimate	ODE Estimate	Real	ANN Estimate	ODE Estimate
1	-0,33	0,96	:	0,24	-0,6	7,77	7,77	7,77	7,77	7,77	7,77	7,77	7,77	7,77	7,77	7,77	7,77
2,0287	0,4505	0,3316	:	0,66	-1,3199	7,2764	7,2764	7,2764	7,2764	7,2764	7,2764	7,2764	7,2764	7,2764	7,2764	7,2764	7,2764
4,828	4,523408971	4,216077309	:	7,090106069	7,419498681	7,77	7,77	7,77	7,77	7,77	7,77	7,77	7,77	7,77	7,77	7,77	7,77
76,1	78,3	78,1	:	95,9	90,4	94	94	94	94	94	94	94	94	94	94	94	94
75,3305	78,468	78,036	:	95,525	90,5201	93,9593	93,9593	93,9593	93,9593	93,9593	93,9593	93,9593	93,9593	93,9593	93,9593	93,9593	93,9593
69,9607	72,739777	75,126243	:	94,513955	94,311557	94	94	94	94	94	94	94	94	94	94	94	94
49,6	49,6	49,6	:	45,1	44,1	43,2	43,2	43,2	43,2	43,2	43,2	43,2	43,2	43,2	43,2	43,2	43,2
49,4714	49,7018	49,6232	:	45,7187	44,19	43,2878	43,2878	43,2878	43,2878	43,2878	43,2878	43,2878	43,2878	43,2878	43,2878	43,2878	43,2878
49,8582	49,75419	49,62755	:	43,85913	43,53388	43,2	43,2	43,2	43,2	43,2	43,2	43,2	43,2	43,2	43,2	43,2	43,2
8,4	8,4	8,4	:	9,7	10,2	10,3	10,3	10,3	10,3	10,3	10,3	10,3	10,3	10,3	10,3	10,3	10,3
8,3853	8,3331	8,4827	:	9,8372	10,448	10,249	10,249	10,249	10,249	10,249	10,249	10,249	10,249	10,249	10,249	10,249	10,249
9,1389	8,979006	8,86267	:	10,23767	10,26889	10,3	10,3	10,3	10,3	10,3	10,3	10,3	10,3	10,3	10,3	10,3	10,3
3350,79	3292,35	3237,61	:	259,98	254,64	254,32	254,32	254,32	254,32	254,32	254,32	254,32	254,32	254,32	254,32	254,32	254,32
3350,4	3290,7	3239,1	:	243,6	255,3	251,3	251,3	251,3	251,3	251,3	251,3	251,3	251,3	251,3	251,3	251,3	251,3
3343,6	3236,107	3129,138	:	237,0021	245,0388	254,3	254,3	254,3	254,3	254,3	254,3	254,3	254,3	254,3	254,3	254,3	254,3
78,3	80,5	80,5	:	92,6	89,5	91,8	91,8	91,8	91,8	91,8	91,8	91,8	91,8	91,8	91,8	91,8	91,8
78,3526	80,6362	80,2248	:	92,6193	89,4776	91,8325	91,8325	91,8325	91,8325	91,8325	91,8325	91,8325	91,8325	91,8325	91,8325	91,8325	91,8325
76,4482	77,6796248	78,68532639	:	91,93562823	91,89664908	91,8	91,8	91,8	91,8	91,8	91,8	91,8	91,8	91,8	91,8	91,8	91,8

The performance indicators of both models are presented in Table 9, compared with the actual values in Table 2. According to these results, it is seen in Table 9 that both the linear ODE system model and the ANN model are successful in predicting the variables presented in Table 1, but the ANN model performance is more successful.

Table 9

Performances of the Estimation Results of ODE and ANN Models

Prediction Type	For x		For y		For z		For h		For f		For g	
	ANN	ODE	ANN	ODE	ANN	ODE	ANN	ODE	ANN	ODE	ANN	ODE
Total Absolute Error	61,2153	445,344	36,107	611,9953	14,5396	97,3422	10,0921	67,93	834,55	5257,563	15,8109	342,461
MAD	0,4858	3,5345	0,2866	4,8571	0,1154	0,772557	0,0801	0,5391	6,6234	41,7267	0,1255	2,7179
MSE	0,6054	25,1231	0,2012	41,6032	0,037858	0,8835	0,0140	0,5260	96,075	2596,224	0,0362	13,1007
RMSE	0,7781	5,0123	0,4486	6,4501	0,19457	0,9400	0,1185	0,7253	9,8018	50,9532	0,1903	3,6195
MAPE	0,5610	6,1495	0,0034	0,0582	0,002481	0,0169	0,0072	0,0489	0,0164	0,0013	0,0015	0,0332
R-Squared	0,9741	0,0101	0,9981	0,6094	0,988446	0,7314	0,9943	0,7859	0,9998	0,9957	0,9994	0,7688

However, when time-dependent estimates are taken into consideration, differential equations come to the forefront because they reveal the instantaneous changes of the variable over time. The activation functions in ANN models estimate the output variable depending on the current states of the variables.

6. IMPACT ANALYSIS

In this section, the relevant activation equation obtained by ANN analysis and given in equation (2) and whose coefficients are given in Table 4 are taken into consideration. Here, the effect of 5 input variables on the estimation of the remaining variable value is investigated. In this context, since there are differences between the magnitudes of the input variable values, the normalized values of all input variables with min-max are taken into account. In addition, the best activation function, which gives a lower MSE value for each variable, is used. The impact matrix for the analysis is given in (4).

$$E = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \quad (4)$$

First, let's consider the variable x , which represents the US Dollar exchange rate accepted as an investment instrument. Thus, with the help of this function, in order to measure the effect of the variables y_{norm} , z_{norm} , h_{norm} , f_{norm} and g_{norm} on the variable x_{norm} , the variable x_{norm} was calculated repeatedly by leaving all input variables at minimum (= 0) and making the value of the variable whose effect was investigated at maximum (= 1). The value of x_{norm} was found by calculating all column values of the E matrix in the activation function. The values of the first column represent the situation where all input variables have no effect, that is, when all variables are at minimum, the values of the second column represent the situation where only the variable y_{norm} is at maximum, the values of the third column represent the situation where only the variable z_{norm} is at maximum, and thus the values of the sixth column represent the situation where the variable g_{norm} is at maximum, respectively. The values of 1 in the matrices were taken into account to represent the maximum values of the normalized input variables. With a similar mindset, the remaining 5 variable process steps were performed respectively and the relevant results are given in Table 10.

Table 10

Impact Analysis Results

V	For x_{norm}		For y_{norm}		For z_{norm}		For h_{norm}		For f_{norm}		For g_{norm}	
	A	B	A	B	A	B	A	B	A	B	A	B
None	0,69	-	0,56	-	1,50	-	-103,17	-	0,70	-	0,24	-
x_{norm}	-	-	0,56	0,46	0,86	-43,02	-39,96	61,27	-0,15	-122,02	0,51	111,17
y_{norm}	-1,07	-255,07	-	-	0,92	-38,66	-35,99	65,12	1,18	68,01	0,69	185,73
z_{norm}	0,13	-81,16	-0,13	-123,03	-	-	-0,03	99,97	0,66	-5,56	0,00	-98,35
h_{norm}	4,88	607,25	0,45	-20,16	-0,20	-113,43	-	-	0,18	-73,76	0,46	89,58
f_{norm}	3,69	434,78	0,44	-22,32	1,44	-4,43	0,43	100,42	-	-	-0,53	-318,03
g_{norm}	0,22	-68,12	0,68	19,96	0,57	-61,78	-13,37	87,04	0,34	-51,89	-	-

V: Max Variable (just one)
A: The Predicted Variable Value
B: The change (%)

Considering the results in Table 10, the values in the first column (A) show the x_{norm} values corresponding to each column value of the effect matrix shown in (4) for the normalized input values. In this sense, when all remaining variables are minimum (=0), $x_{norm}=0.69$, and only when y_{norm} is maximum (=1) $x_{norm} = -1.07$, only when z_{norm} is maximum (=1) $x_{norm} = 0.13$, only when h_{norm} is maximum (=1) $x_{norm} = 4.88$, only when f_{norm} is maximum (=1) $x_{norm} = 3.69$, and only when g_{norm} is maximum (=1) $x_{norm} = 0.22$. Therefore, compared to the situation where all variables are at their minimum, the percentage change in the x_{norm} variable is -255.07% for y_{norm} , -81.16% for z_{norm} , 607.25% for h_{norm} , 434.78% for f_{norm} , and -68.12% for g_{norm} . Calculations were performed for other variables using this approach. Thus, considering the column values in Table 10, the relationship between the variables is presented in Table 11.

Translated with DeepL.com (free version) In this sense, when all the remaining variables are minimum (= 0) $x_{norm}=0.69$, when only y_{norm} is maximum (= 1) $x_{norm}=-1.07$, when only z_{norm} is maximum (= 1) $x_{norm}=0.13$, when only h_{norm} is maximum (= 1) $x_{norm}=4.88$, when only f_{norm} is maximum (= 1) $x_{norm}=3.69$ and when only g_{norm} is maximum (= 1) $x_{norm}=0.22$. Therefore, the percentage change in the x_{norm} variable compared to the case when all variables are minimum is obtained as -255.07% for y_{norm} , -81.16% for z_{norm} , 607.25% for h_{norm} , 434.78% for f_{norm} and -68.12% for g_{norm} . Calculations were made for other variables with this way of thinking. Thus, considering the column values of Table 10, the relationship between the variables is presented in Table 11.

Table 11

The effects of normalized variables on each other according to the ANN activation function.

	For x_{norm}	For y_{norm}	For z_{norm}	For h_{norm}	For f_{norm}	For g_{norm}
x_{norm}		-	-	+	+	-
y_{norm}	+		-	-	-	+
z_{norm}	-	-		-	-	-
h_{norm}	+	+	+		+	+
f_{norm}	-	+	-	-		-
g_{norm}	+	+	+	+	-	

8. CONCLUSIONS

In this study, the dynamic behaviors of key macroeconomic and financial indicators in the Turkish economy—such as exchange rates, interest rates, inflation, economic growth, financial market indices, and external economic risks—were analyzed over the period 2014–2024 using both a linear ordinary differential equation (ODE) system and artificial neural network (ANN) models. The performance of these models was compared, and the interactions among economic variables were examined in detail.

8.1. Model Performance and Prediction Accuracy

The Turkish economy has experienced numerous internal and external uncertainties and shocks over the past decade. During this period, sharp and sudden fluctuations were observed especially in exchange rates and other macroeconomic indicators. The ODE model demonstrated important advantages in mathematically representing time-dependent instantaneous changes and interpreting linear interactions among economic variables. However, due to the complex and often nonlinear nature of the economy, the ANN model showed superior predictive performance.

Performance metrics such as Mean Absolute Error (MAE), Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE), and R-squared indicated that the ANN outperformed the ODE model. Particularly in variables like economic growth, interest rates, and exchange rates, the ANN effectively captured complex nonlinear relationships, highlighting the structural vulnerabilities and external openness of the Turkish economy.

8.2. Interactions Among Economic Variables

The impact analysis provided insights into the interdependencies among variables in the Turkish economy. The exchange rate was found to be positively influenced most strongly by economic growth and the financial market index. During periods of rapid economic growth—such as prior to the 2017–2018 period—increased investment and consumer demand led to higher demand for foreign currency, pushing exchange rates upward. Similarly, increased liquidity and capital inflows in financial markets exerted upward pressure on the exchange rate.

Conversely, variables representing political uncertainty, geopolitical risks, and external shocks showed negative effects on the exchange rate. Notably, the 2018 currency crisis and the 2020 COVID-19 pandemic demonstrated the tangible impacts of these negative influences, underscoring the critical importance of political and economic stability for exchange rate and financial stability in emerging markets like Turkey. Interest rates exhibited a complex relationship with exchange rates, displaying both positive and negative effects. The Central Bank of the Republic of Turkey's monetary policies directly and indirectly affect exchange rates, and this effect varies according to market expectations and investor behavior over time.

8.3. Policy Implications for the Turkish Economy

The findings of this study offer important policy implications for Turkey. The strong positive effects of economic growth and financial market conditions on

exchange rates highlight the priority of fostering sustainable growth and deepening financial markets to maintain financial stability. At the same time, the negative impact of external risks and political uncertainty on exchange rates emphasizes the need for effective macroeconomic and political risk management strategies to ensure economic stability.

Given the complex effects of interest rates on exchange rates, the Central Bank's monetary policy decisions must closely monitor market expectations, capital flows, and international developments, employing policy tools flexibly to maintain stability.

8.4. Future Directions in Modeling Approaches

While ODE models effectively capture instantaneous dynamics and crisis-period behaviors, ANN models excel in predicting complex, nonlinear, and multivariate systems. For an externally exposed and vulnerable economy like Turkey, hybrid modeling approaches combining both techniques can offer substantial benefits for both short-term interventions and long-term planning.

Future research should explore seasonal effects, policy changes, and global economic conditions in more detail, expand datasets, and integrate additional macroeconomic variables into models. Furthermore, analyzing the impacts of unexpected shocks such as pandemics will provide valuable insights for strengthening Turkey's economic resilience and informing policy development.

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